

**DOBRE PRAKSE U KOMUNIKACIJI I DISEMINACIJI ZNAČAJNIH
REZULTATA PROJEKATA FINANSIRANIH OD STRANE EU****GOOD PRACTICES IN THE COMMUNICATION AND
DISSEMINATION OF SIGNIFICANT RESULTS OF EU-FUNDED
PROJECTS****Sandra Kolarić¹, Jelena Spajić², Mladen Radišić³, Danijela Lalić⁴, Maja
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Apstrakt: Ovaj članak istražuje dobre prakse u diseminaciji i komunikaciji evropskih projekata. Cilj rada je da analizira kako tri inicijative iz programa Horizont Evropa - STELAR, Farmtopia i InPlasTwin - primenjuju ove prakse u realnom okruženju. Iako su komunikacija i diseminacija od ključnog značaja za pretvaranje istraživanja u konkretan uticaj, one su i dalje nedovoljno proučene i često se nedosledno sprovode u okviru EU projekata. Ovo istraživanje popunjava taj jaz identifikovanjem efektivnih, prenosivih strategija zasnovanih na dostavljenim izveštajima, veb-sajtovima i društvenim mrežama. STELAR predstavlja zaokružen primer, Farmtopia se ističe kroz Open Call aktivnosti, dok InPlasTwin naglasak stavlja na izgradnju kapaciteta. Nalazi pružaju praktične smernice za buduće projekte programa Horizont Evropa u unapređenju vidljivosti, angažovanja stejkholdera i razmene znanja.

Ključne reči: Diseminacija, komunikacija, evropski projekti, Horizont Evropa

Abstract: This article explores good practices in dissemination and communication of European projects. Its aim is to analyse how three Horizon Europe initiatives - STELAR, Farmtopia and InPlasTwin - apply these practices in real settings. Despite being vital for translating research into impact, communication and dissemination remain underexplored and often inconsistently applied across EU projects. This study addresses this gap by identifying effective, transferable strategies based on deliverables, websites and social media. STELAR offers a complete example, Farmtopia excels in Open Calls, and InPlasTwin in capacity-building. The findings provide practical guidance for future Horizon Europe projects to enhance visibility, stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange.

Keywords: Dissemination, communication, European projects, Horizon Europe

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the European Commission, the European Union implements its strategic priorities and policies through a wide range of funding programmes established under the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021–2027 and NextGenerationEU. Some of these programmes include Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, Interreg and LIFE, designed to support research and innovation, cooperation, skills development, and environmental and climate action across the EU (European Commission, [5]).

Horizon Europe is the programme designed to confront climate change, advance the UN Sustainable Development Goals and at the same time reinforce the EU's economic and global standing. It amplifies the reach and policy relevance of research and innovation addressing major societal and environmental challenges (European Commission, [5]). The European Commission emphasises that public investment in research should convert ideas developed in laboratories into innovative products and services capable of reaching the market, generating economic growth, employment, and improved living standards across the EU and beyond (Campos, A., & Codina, L., 2021).

Researchers supported by the European Union generate numerous findings each year, but these only reach their full potential when shared with those best positioned to use them making results accessible and impactful beyond academia. Dissemination goes beyond publishing scientific papers; making results accessible so researchers, industry, policymakers, and others can apply them. This highlights societal relevance, encourages scientific uptake, and opens pathways for new products, services, and opportunities (European Commission, [4]).

Communication is a vital component of EU-funded projects, increasing visibility, ensuring transparency, raising public awareness of EU fund use, and facilitating engagement with partners and stakeholders (European Commission, 2021). Effective communication requires clear messages and appropriate channels for each audience, supporting project success during implementation and sustaining impact afterward. Close collaboration with stakeholders and end-users enhances knowledge exchange, fosters innovation, and improves the uptake of results by decision-makers, industry, and academia (Henriksson, Ruoslahti & Hyttinen, 2018).

This paper focuses on three Horizon Europe projects and analyses their best practices in communicating and disseminating key results, with the aim of identifying lessons that can be transferred to future initiatives.

2. SELECTION CRITERIA AND SOURCES OF DATA

Projects were selected to represent diverse yet comparable Horizon Europe initiatives, each providing distinct communication and dissemination experiences. *STELAR* represents a completed project with a full communication and dissemination cycle.

Farmtopia demonstrates how a Horizon Europe project integrates an Open Call and promotes it. *InPlasTwin* highlights scientific collaboration and capacity-building actions.

Information was collected from publicly available deliverables where possible, and supplemented with content from official project websites, news updates, social media posts, and the European Commission’s CORDIS portal.

3. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

“Good practice” is defined as communication and dissemination actions that are clearly planned, well executed and demonstrate measurable engagement with target audiences. “Significant results” refers to outputs that have a tangible impact - for example, producing platforms or toolkits, increasing uptake of Open Calls, generating open-access publications or building lasting capacity among stakeholders. Table 1 provides an overview of the three selected projects, including their names, funding type/call, duration, and the main goal of each.

Table 1: Overview of Selected Projects

Project name	Funding type/ Call	Duration	Main goal
STELAR (Knowledge Lake Management System) (STELAR Website, 2022)	Horizon Europe – HORIZON-CL4-2021-DATA-01-03 (Innovation Action) No. 101070122	1 Sept 2022 – 31 Aug 2025 (36 months)	Design, develop and evaluate a Knowledge Lake Management System (KLMS) – a platform and set of tools enabling simple and intelligent data discovery, AI-ready data, and semantic interoperability for smart agriculture & food safety.
Farmtopia (Democratizing Digital Farming) (Farmtopia deliverable, 2023)	Horizon Europe – HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-02-04-two-stage (Innovation Action) No. 101083541	1 Sept 2023 – 31 Aug 2026 (36 months)	Democratise digital farming by making Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) accessible, affordable and tailored to small farms. Includes an Open Call to bring in additional solutions.
InPlasTwin (Increasing expertise in micro- and nanoplastics analysis through twinning action) (Cordis, 2024)	Horizon Europe – HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02 / Topic 02-01 (Coordination and Support Action) Project No. 101160289	1 Oct 2024 – 30 Sept 2027 (36 months)	Advance understanding of micro- and nanoplastic impacts in environment and food (focus on strawberries). Enhance partner skills through knowledge exchange and training on MNP extraction, identification, and characterisation, fostering an inclusive, skilled scientific community.

Following this, Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of these projects based on their communication and dissemination activities.

Table 2: Comparative Analysis of Selected Projects

Category	STELAR	Farmtopia	InPlasTwin
Visual Identity & Branding	Consistent visual identity via brand book; creative promo items	Consistent visual identity; combines traditional and modern elements;	Consistent visual identity; reflects project narrative and core values
Multi-Channel Approach	Website, 6 social media profiles, newsletter, amplification through partner channels	Website, 6 social media profiles, newsletter, amplification through partner channels	Website, 5 social media profiles, newsletter, amplification through partner channels
Website Specific Features	News, blogs, infographics; media partnerships; KLMS platform and Toolkit	News, blogs, infographics; "Farmtopia Ecosystem" section	News, blogs; Capacity-building section + Synergy page
SEO & Analytics	Uses SEO and analytics to monitor & reach	Uses SEO and analytics to monitor & reach	SEO and analytics not confirmed.
Events, training & interactive outreach	Participation at events, fairs, open days and webinars with interactive demos, quizzes and showcases	Participation at events, fairs, open days and webinars with interactive demos, quizzes and showcases	Participation at events, fair, open days, webinars, workshops, trainings, staff exchanges, and showcases
Media outreach & content production	Press releases via partners/media contacts/Prowly, media statements, featured articles in magazines and online portals, editorial backlinks, interviews with experts ; "Data Stories 360" podcast;	Press releases via partners/media contacts/Prowly, media statements, featured articles in magazines and online portals, editorial backlinks	No openly accessible information could be found regarding its media outreach and content production
Ecosystem & synergies	Cooperation with EU initiatives and sister projects	Collaboration with EU initiatives, Digital Innovation Hubs,	Cooperation with sister projects, planning joint

Category	STELAR	Farmtopia	InPlasTwin
	through joint activities such as events, joint press releases, etc.	AKIS; MoUs, joint workshops	activities, thematic events and other actions.
Scientific publications/ Open Access	Peer-reviewed papers, conference contributions, technical briefs; open access	Peer-reviewed papers, conference contributions, practice abstracts, policy briefs; open access	Open Access articles and conference contributions; more publications planned

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

All three projects began with a clearly defined visual identity - logo, brand book, templates, and offline materials - to ensure consistency across partners and channels. Longer-running projects like STELAR and Farmtopia show that branding and websites must evolve with feedback, underscoring the value of continuous adaptation. STELAR also used creative promo items (anti-stress balls, bookmarks, lens-cleaning tissues) to extend its presence beyond events and reinforce the brand.

Each project employs a multi-channel communication strategy to reach different audiences and showcase activities, events, publications, and results in accessible, engaging formats. In STELAR, YouTube hosted recordings of webinars, Open Days, and other events for on-demand access to project knowledge.

Websites (Picture 1) serve as central hubs for news, results, and stakeholder engagement. STELAR and Farmtopia applied SEO and analytics to maximise visibility, while no information is available for InPlasTwin. Dedicated sections, such as Farmtopia's "Ecosystem," highlight sister projects, synergies, and media partnerships. STELAR's website provides access to key results, the KLMS platform, and Toolkit, while InPlasTwin features a capacity-building section with trainings, staff exchanges, and knowledge-transfer activities.

Picture 1: STELAR and Farmtopia websites.

Scientific knowledge is disseminated via peer-reviewed papers, conference contributions, technical briefs, and other open-access outputs. Projects promote these materials through websites, social media, and platforms such as Zenodo, EU-FarmBook, Medium, Open Research Europe, and GitHub, ensuring broad reuse and uptake by researchers and practitioners.

Stakeholder engagement occurs through webinars, Open Days, workshops, thematic meetings, and sector fairs, enabling projects to present results, demonstrate technologies, collect feedback, and build trust. Open Days, in particular, provide interactive platforms for demonstrations and informal discussions.

Projects also collaborate with related EU initiatives, sister projects, and innovation hubs to exchange knowledge, foster synergies, and enhance visibility. Joint webinars, events, papers, and press releases support two-way knowledge exchange and further extend each project's reach and credibility.

While these projects share many similarities, they differ in focus and implementation. As a completed project, STELAR had more time to promote its key results, enabling more media outreach and content production that supported direct knowledge exchange and demonstrated practical applications. Meanwhile, Farmtopia focused on promoting its Open Call via a dedicated webpage, social media, webinars, and sectoral presentations. While InPlasTwin focuses on capacity building, trainings, staff exchanges, and knowledge-transfer activities to strengthen partner expertise and skills. Farmtopia targeted broader audiences, while InPlasTwin used science-oriented communication within research and academia.

5. TRANSFERABLE PRACTICES AND POTENTIAL CHALLENGES

Several practices are transferable to other initiatives: clear visual identity and branding, multi-channel communication, regular stakeholder engagement, and dedicated initiatives such as media outreach, podcasts, or Open Calls. While open science practices such as publishing peer-reviewed papers, conference contributions and technical briefs on openly accessible platforms can maximise reuse, citations and uptake, they may pose challenges for projects with limited resources, shorter timelines, or sensitive data that cannot be fully shared publicly.

Furthermore, challenges can occur when partners do not provide the necessary information or when the technology does not advance as planned. To address this, establishing clear communication protocols and regular progress reviews can help ensure transparency and timely information sharing. Presenting complex innovations in a clear and understandable way for different target groups can also be difficult; therefore, using tailored communication materials and visual storytelling may enhance comprehension. Additionally, reaching or gaining access to certain stakeholders may be

limited, which can affect engagement and the dissemination of project results. Developing targeted outreach strategies and leveraging existing networks could mitigate these limitations.

6. CONCLUSION

The literature highlights that effective communication and dissemination are crucial for maximizing the impact of EU-funded research, ensuring results reach beyond academic publications, engage diverse stakeholders, and foster collaboration with end-users. The analysis of the Horizon Europe projects - STELAR, Farmtopia, and InPlasTwin - shows these principles are largely implemented in practice. Each project applied communication and dissemination strategies aligned with its focus: STELAR on promoting results, Farmtopia on its Open Call and ecosystem, and InPlasTwin on capacity-building and knowledge transfer. Collectively, these projects demonstrate how structured communication strategies enhance societal relevance, stakeholder engagement, and practical application of research outcomes.

For future European projects, it is recommended to invest in consistent and flexible branding, multi-channel communication including SEO and Open Science practices, and interactive events that foster collaboration with related initiatives and innovation hubs to create lasting synergies. Finally, further research could explore the measurable impact of these communication strategies on broader audiences and the uptake of project results, as well as the effectiveness of different event formats and tailored approaches for engaging diverse stakeholder groups.

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